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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF URINARY ALBUMIN LEVELS IN EARLY
DETECTION OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY**¹Dr. Uzma Abbas, ²Dr. Wajeeda Fatima¹PMDC # 92873-P. ²Pmdc # 97438-P**Article Received:** August 2020**Accepted:** September 2020**Published:** October 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To analyze the values of combined detection of urinary micro albumin (mAlb), α 1-microglobulin (α 1-MG) and N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG) in the early diagnosis of diabetic nephropathy (DN).

Methods: Ninety-four patients with early DN who were admitted to the Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan between April 2016 and April 2017 were selected and set as a DN group. Moreover, seventy-six patients with diabetes who were admitted to the hospital in the same period were selected and set as a diabetes group, and sixty-four healthy people were selected as set as a control group. The urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG of the three groups were detected. Moreover, the patients were divided into a favorable blood glucose control group and a poor blood glucose control group according to the blood glucose control condition of the patients. The detection results of the three groups were compared and statistically analyzed.

Results: The urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels of the DN group were significantly higher than those of the diabetes group and control group, and the differences had statistical significance ($P < 0.05$). The detection indicator values of the favorable blood glucose control group were much lower than those of the poor blood glucose control group, and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). The positive rate of the combined detection of mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels was 90.2%, which was much higher than that of single indicator ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Combined detection of urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG is sensitive in diagnosing early renal damages in DN patients.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Uzma Abbas,**PMDC # 92873-P. Email: star920@yahoo.com

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is the major complication of diabetic microangiopathy. Early renal damages are difficult to be discovered because there are no obvious clinical manifestations in the early stage and results of conventional test items such as urinary protein, urea nitrogen and creatinine are usually normal. But the kidney has manifested apparent pathological changes before the appearance of albuminuria. DN can be irreversible and even evolve to terminal stage once renal impairment and persistent proteinuria occur. [1,2] Therefore, the early diagnosis and inhibiting or delaying the occurrence and development of nephropathy are the important subjects in the current clinical research. [3] To enhance the early diagnostic accuracy of DN, detection of relevant indicators is usually used for assisting diagnosis. This study discussed the values of the combined detection of mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG in the early diagnosis of DN by analyzing 94 DN patients, 76 diabetes patients and 64 healthy people from the Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan, aiming to provide an evidence for the formulation of treatment scheme in clinics.

METHODS:

Ninety-four patients with early DN who were admitted to the Services Hospital between April 2016 and April 2017 were selected and set as a DN group. Moreover, 76 patients with diabetes who were admitted to the hospital in the same period were selected and set as a diabetes group. Patients in both groups were diagnosed following WHO diabetes diagnostic criteria. [4] The patients in the DN group had negative urine protein and 20 ~ 200 mg/24 h urinary albumin excretion rate, suggesting the manifestations of early renal injury. None of them had allergy, connective tissue diseases and renal lesions induced by infection or tumor or complications such as ketoacidosis and heart failure. Those who previously took drugs and hormones which can induce albuminuria and renal toxic drugs were excluded.

In the DN group, there were 52 males and 42 females, with an average age of 50.1 \pm 5.7 years (35~73 years) and an average disease course of 7.3 \pm 2.2 years (3~12 years); in the diabetes group, there were 43 males and 33 females, with an average age of 51.3 \pm 6.1 years (36~74 years) and an average disease course of 7.1 \pm 2.0 years (3~11 years). Sixty-four people who went to the hospital to receive physical examination and obtained normal examination results were selected and set as a control group. In the control group, there were 35 males and 29 females, with an average age of 50.2 \pm 8.9 years (33~76 years). The differences of gender, age and disease course between the three groups had no

statistical significance ($P > 0.05$). This study has been reviewed and approved by the ethics committee of the Sheikh Zayed Hospital, Rahim Yar Khan, and the patients have signed an informed consent.

Specimen collection: 10 mL of fresh morning urine was collected from each subject and then centrifuged at 3000 r/min at a radius of 12 cm for 10 minutes. Then the supernate was separated and preserved at -20 °C. Moreover, 3 mL of fasting venous blood was collected from each subject on the same day. Serum was separated and detected for haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c).

Detection methods: DXC800 fully automatic biochemical analyzer (Beckman, USA) and reagents which were purchased from Roche Diagnostics GmbH Co., Ltd. in German and Beijing Leadman Biochemical Inc. in Pakistan. Urinary mAlb was detected using enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Urinary α 1-MG was detected using radiation and scattering turbidimetry. Urinary NAG was determined using endpoint method. All the detection procedures strictly followed instructions. The mAlb level lower than 20 mg/L, α 1-MG lower than 15 mg/L and NAG lower than 15.7 U/L were determined as normal. HbA1c was measured using thin-column method. Control of blood glucose was evaluated as favorable if HbA1c was lower than 7%. The procedures followed the instructions. The item quality was controlled and non-specific disturbance was excluded to ensure the accuracy of results.

Statistical analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Measurement data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and processed by t test. Enumeration data were expressed as % and processed by Chi-square test. Difference was considered as statistically significant if $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:**Detection results of urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and**

NAG levels: The urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels of patients in the DN group were significantly higher than those of the diabetes group and control, suggesting statistically significant differences ($P < 0.05$; Table-I).

Correlation between blood glucose condition and various indicators:

The detection of HbA1c demonstrated that, 97 patients had favorable control of blood glucose and 73 patients had poor control. The HbA1c, mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels of the poor blood glucose control group were higher than those of the favorable control group, and the differences were statistically remarkable (Table-II).

Table-I: Comparison of mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels between the three groups.

Group	n	mAlb(mg/L)	α 1-MG(mg/L)	NAG(U/L)
DN group	94	48.54 \pm 5.68* [#]	16.03 \pm 3.64* [#]	18.08 \pm 0.52* [#]
Diabetes group	76	9.72 \pm 5.03	7.67 \pm 2.21	10.23 \pm 1.08
Control group	64	5.69 \pm 4.93	3.43 \pm 2.75	9.41 \pm 0.77

Note: * indicated P<0.05 compared to the control group; [#] indicated P<0.05 compared to the diabetes group.

Table-II: Comparison of levels of indicators between groups with different blood glucose control.

Group	N	HbA1c(%)	mAlb(mg/L)	α 1-MG(mg/L)	NAG(U/L)
Favorable blood glucose control group	97	6.22 \pm 0.56*	10.14 \pm 5.30*	4.58 \pm 2.13*	11.09 \pm 1.02*
Poor blood glucose control group	73	14.07 \pm 1.73	45.11 \pm 9.22	18.14 \pm 3.37	20.14 \pm 2.68

Note: * indicated P<0.05 compared to the poor blood glucose control group.

The positive rates of detection based on single indicators and multiple indicators in the DN group:

The positive rate of detection based on urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG was higher than that based on single indicators, and the difference had statistical significance (P<0.05; Table-III).

DISCUSSION:

It is reported that, the incidence of DN is 10% among patients who have suffered from diabetes for more than five years and 20%~30% among patients who have suffered for more than ten years.⁵ In early stage of DN, the reduced negative charge components on glomerular basement membrane and the increased diameter of filtration pores on glomerular filtration membrane increases the excretion volume of proteins with moderate molecular weight. [6] In physiological state, mAlb which is a micro proteins with a molecular

weight of 69 kD and negative charges are usually unable to pass through filtration barriers due to the effects of pore size barriers and charge barriers. Once the integrity of glomeruli is damaged, the filtration of micro proteins increases. The appearance of albuminuria and the increased level of albuminuria are associated with the extent of damage of glomeruli.^{7,8} Urinary mAlb in the early stage of DN is usually more sensitive to routine urine test and renal function examination. The level of urinary mAlb increases significantly even if glomeruli experience mild damages. The results of this study suggested that the output volume of urinary mAlb of the patients with early DN was significantly higher than that of the control group. To discover early renal damages, detection of urinary mAlb is regarded as a conventional test item for DN patients.

Table-III: Comparison of positive rates of detection based on single indicators and multiple indicators in the DN group.

Indicators	No. of positive	Positive
	cases(n)	rate(%)
mAlb	64	68.1
α 1-MG	59	62.8
NAG	67	71.3
mAlb+ α 1-MG+NAG	85	90.4*

Note: * indicated P<0.05 compared to detection based on single indicator.

α 1-MG is a kind of glycoprotein synthesized by the liver and lymphocyte. The α 1-MG with a molecular weight of 3.3 kD can pass through glomeruli freely,

and 99% of them is reabsorbed and metabolized by renal tubules. When the reabsorption function of renal tubules is failed, the output volume of α 1-MG will

increase.^{9,10} In the early stage of DN, renal tubular epithelial cells fail to act as barriers because its structural integrity is damaged due to ischemia, inflammation and toxic substances; as a result, the reabsorption function fails, which leads to the remarkable increase of excretion volume. [11] The results of this study suggested that the excretion volume of urinary α 1-MG of patients with early DN was much higher than that of healthy people and patients with diabetes, indicating renal tubules have been damaged in the early stage of DN. Therefore, α 1-MG is considered as one of the early sensitive markers for DN.

NAG, a kind of hydrolase, is extensively distributed in organs. NAG with a molecular weight of 130000 is not easy to be filtered by glomeruli. But when kidney convoluted tubules are damaged, lysosome will release a large amount of NAG, leading to the obvious increase of NAG in urine. [12,13] It has been pointed out that NAG can be regarded as a sensitive marker for renal tubular damage. [14] In the early stage of DN, the increase of glomeruli filtration pressure, the reduction of negative charges on filtration membrane and changes of gaping holes induce the increased filtration of proteins, activation of lysosome and increase of urinary NAG. [15,16] The activity of urinary NAG is abnormal even when the excretion rate of urine proteins is normal. Therefore, the detection of activity changes of urinary NAG of patients with diabetes is beneficial to the early diagnosis of DN.

In this study, the mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG levels of patients in the favorable blood glucose control group and poor blood glucose control group were detected. The results demonstrated that the levels of the three indicators of the latter group were higher than those of the former group, suggesting mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG can reflect the renal damages and blood glucose control conditions of patients with diabetes. The joint detection of the three indicators can improve the detection rate of early DN and help clinical doctors formulate scientific and reasonable intervention measures to effectively control blood glucose and promote the recovery of renal functions. Moreover, the mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG of the DN patients were observed to explore the clinical values of detection of single indicator or joint detection of multiple indicators in the early diagnosis of DN. Table-III demonstrates that the positive rate of joint detection of the three indicators was 90.4%, which was significantly different with the positive rates of detection of single indicator. It suggests that joint detection of multiple indicators is superior to detection of single indicator.

CONCLUSION:

Urinary mAlb, α 1-MG and NAG can be regarded as the sensitive indicators for early diagnosis of DN. Joint detection of the three indicators before the appearance of proteinuria in DN patients can significantly improve the positive rate of DN diagnosis and is beneficial to the early diagnosis of renal injury, and moreover the levels of the three indicators can be used to identify the severity and location of DN early and reflect treatment effect, suggesting certain clinical values to the occurrence, development and treatment efficacy of DN.

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Research Article

DETERMINATION OF VARIATIONS IN ETIOLOGIES OF HYPOXIC ACUTE KIDNEY DAMAGE AMONG NEWBORNS

¹Dr. Ifra Afzal, ²Dr. Uzma Abbas, ³Dr. Muhammad Shair Ismail

¹PMDC # 106555-P., ²PMDC # 92873-P., ³PMDC # 107489-P.

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine association of in-hospital outcome of AKI with etiology in newborns at a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Pediatric Neonatology, Services Hospital, Lahore by using non-probability purposive sampling technique from June 2016 to June 2017. A total of 101 newborns diagnosed with acute kidney injury were registered. Etiological factors were assessed and these patients were followed till discharge to monitor in-hospital outcomes.

Results: Of these 101 newborns, 75 (74.3%) were boys while 26 (25.7%) were girls. Mean age of these newborns was 7.59 ± 6.13 days (range; 1 day to 28 days). Mean age of the boys was 5.73 ± 7.20 days while that of girls was 6.77 ± 6.16 days. ($p=0.515$). Mean weight of these neonates was 2545.05 ± 600.42 grams (range; 1000 grams to 4000 grams). Mean serum potassium level was 4.94 ± 0.92 mgEq/L ranging from 3.1 mgEq/L to 7.0 mgEq/L. Mean urea level was 73.35 ± 27.65 mg/dl ranging from 18 mg/dl to 206 mg/dl. Mean serum creatinine level was 1.98 ± 0.27 mg/dl, ranging from 1.6 mg/dl to 2.8 mg/dl. Mean serum sodium level was 145.72 ± 12.64 mgEq/L ranging from 126 to 166 mEq/L. Eighty one (80.2%) were term babies while 20 (19.8%) were pre-term babies. Of these 101 study cases, 29 (28.7%) delivered vaginally while 72 (71.3%) through cesarean section. Delayed crying was noted in 48 (47.5%), dehydration 13 (12.9%), sepsis in 36 (35.6%) and renal malformation in only 4%. Neonatal mortality in these patients was 15 (14.9%) while 86 (85.1%) were discharged from hospital after recovery.

Conclusion: Acute kidney disease in newborns is associated with significant disease morbidity and mortality with asphyxia and sepsis are the main etiological factors responsible. It is predominantly more common in boys compared with girls. Mortality rate was high in our study and it was significantly associated with female gender. Mortality was also associated with elevated serum sodium and urea level.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Ifra Afzal,

PMDC # 106555-P., Email: star920@yahoo.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute kidney injury, formerly referred to as acute renal failure (ARF), is defined as an acute reduction in kidney function that results in a decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) leading to retention of urea and other nitrogenous waste products, and loss of fluid, electrolyte, and acid-base regulation. [1-3] AKI is an important contributing factor to the morbidity and mortality of critically ill neonates. Acute kidney injury refers to consistent increase in the levels of plasma creatinine by more than 1.5 mg/dl for more than 24 hours among full term newborns during their first few days of life provided that mother harbors normal kidney functions. [4,5] Among preterm newborns, serum creatinine levels during their first days of life may not give a true picture of a reflection of the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) as its levels are usually high during first couple of days which then start decreasing gradually within first two weeks. [6]

Acute kidney injury, in different studies, has been reported to be ranging between 8% to 24% while these cases may further be classified in two groups i.e. Oliguric and Non-oliguric. However such reductions in urine output may also be seen in the absence of acute kidney injury, hence cannot be employed as sole criteria for the diagnosis. [7,8]

The cause of AKI among newborns remains to be multi-factorial, and generally there are multiple related contributing agents associated with AKI in neonates. In majority of cases birth asphyxia and sepsis are commonly encountered underlying conditions of AKI in these patients while other conditions in neonates associated with development of AKI may be; dehydration, bleeding, respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), congestive cardiac failure (CCF) and nephrotoxic drug. [9,10]

Among newborns common etiological factors include “Congenital malformations (including renal dysplasia, hypoplasia, agenesis and renal cysts); acquired kidney diseases including acute tubular necrosis, vascular events (renal artery or vein thrombosis), or medications (angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor or indomethacin usage during pregnancy); and obstructive uropathy”. [9,10]

Estimation of serum creatinine levels remains the simplest, robust and widely adopted means for the assessment of kidney functions which drops significantly from 1.1 mg/dl to 0.4 mg/dl during first two weeks of life following term delivery while from 1.3 mg/dl in case of preterm infants. [11-13]

Treatment options may include conservative

management, dialysis and surgical interventions in case of obstructions in urinary tract while peritoneal dialysis is a treatment of choice compared with other dialysis procedures particularly among low birth weight newborns.^{14,15} The onset AKI may also be prenatal congenital disease including renal dysplasia, obstructive uropathy and autosomal recessive polycystic kidney disease while it is commonly acquired in postnatal periods as a result of hypoxic ischemic injuries as well toxic insult.

Nephrotoxic AKI is generally associated with use of aminoglycoside antibiotics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs which are used for closure of patent ductus arteriosus while some studies have also reported genetic risk factors of acute renal failure among neonates. [16]

This study was done to determine association of outcome of AKI with etiological factors of acute kidney injury (AKI) among newborns of Southern Punjab, Pakistan owing to the scarcity of local data on this topic.

METHODS:

This study was done at Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of the Services Hospital, Lahore which provides tertiary care level facilities to the population of 35 million people of Southern Punjab.

A total of 101 newborns with Acute Kidney Injury admitted to the NICU of our hospital were included in this cross-sectional study.

Sample size was calculated by sample size calculator of Epi-info software of CDC by anticipating 20% [17] mortality rate among newborns with AKI i.e. (p=20%), margin of error was 8% among newborns with AKI Newborns of either sex less than 28 days having acute kidney injury were included in this study. AKI was defined as serum creatinine levels more than 1.5 mg/dl irrespective of the age. The newborns were clinically assessed by a consultant pediatrician for different causes of the AKI such as dehydration, sepsis, asphyxia neonatorum and renal malformation. Dehydration was defined by presence of any two of the following conditions; Sunken eyes, dry mucus membrane, having depressed fontanelle, unresponsiveness, lethargy, heart rate more than 160 per minute (tachycardia) and hypotension defined as having systolic blood pressure less than 60 mm Hg. Neonatal sepsis was defined as serum C – reactive protein levels more than 6 mg/dl plus any two of the following conditions; Temperature instability hypothermia characterized as less than 35 C° or hyperthermia (more than 38.5 °F), tachycardia defined

as patient having heart rate 160 per minute, delayed capillary refill time more than three seconds, tachypnea > 60/ minute. Asphyxia neonatorum was defined as if newborn failed to initiate and sustain breathing after 60 seconds of cutting umbilical cord and is related with delayed crying for more than five minutes. Renal malformation was diagnosed ultrasonographically

revealing morphological defects which was reported by a senior Sonologist having more than 10 years of relevant experience. Outcome of AKI in newborns was measured in terms mortality during current hospitalization. Other relevant information like age, gender, gestational age and mode of delivery were also noted in the predesigned study proforma.

Table-I: Cross – tabulation of in-hospital outcome with study variables. (n=101)

Variables	Outcome		P-value	
	Discharged	Death		
Gender	Boys (n=75)	67	08	0.05
	Girls (n=26)	19	07	
Gestation	Term (n=81)	70	11	0.489
	Preterm (n=20)	16	04	
Mode of delivery	Vaginal (n=29)	26	03	0.545
	Cesarean Section (n=72)	60	12	
Delayed Crying	Yes (n=48)	41	07	1.000
	No (n=53)	45	08	
Sepsis	Yes (n=36)	32	04	0.564
	No (n=65)	54	11	
Dehydration	Yes (n=13)	10	03	0.404
	No (n=88)	76	12	
Renal malformation	Yes (n=04)	03	01	0.480
	No (n=97)	83	14	

Data obtained was entered in SPSS version 16 on the computer to analyze mean and standard deviations for the numerical study variables like age (in days), serum creatinine levels (in mg/dl), Serum sodium levels. Gender, mode of delivery, gestation, dehydration, sepsis, delayed crying, renal malformation and outcome (discharged/ expired) were tabulated in terms

of frequencies and percentages. Outcome was cross-tabulated against gender, gestation, mode of delivery, delayed crying, sepsis, renal malformation, dehydration and chisquare test was applied to see their impact on outcome while for numerical variables of the study independent sample t test was used at level of significance of 0.05.

Table-II: Serum Biochemical parameters with regards to in-hospital outcome. (n=101)

Biochemical parameters		Outcome		P-value
		Discha- Rged	Death	
		Serum Potassium Level (mEq/L)	Mean	
	SD	0.86	1.22	
Serum Urea (mg/dl)	Mean	69.35	96.27	0.001
	SD	23.67	37.45	
Serum Sodium level (mEq/L)	Mean	144.62	152.00	0.037
	SD	12.90	9.05	

RESULTS:

We recruited a total of 101 newborns with acute kidney injury. Of these 101 newborns, 75 (74.3%) were boys while 26 (25.7%) were girls. Mean age of these newborns was 7.59 ± 6.13 days (range; 1 day to 28 days). Mean age of the boys was 5.73 ± 7.20 days while that of girls was 6.77 ± 6.16 days.

($p=0.515$). Mean weight of these neonates was 2545.05 ± 600.42 grams (range; 1000 grams to 4000 grams). Mean serum creatinine level was 1.98 ± 0.27 mg/dl, ranging from 1.6 mg/dl to 2.8 mg/dl. Mean serum potassium level was 4.94 ± 0.92 mgEq/L ranging from

3.1 mgEq/L to 7.0 mgEq/L. Mean urea level was 73.35 ± 27.65 mg/dl ranging from 18 mg/dl to 206 mg/dl. Mean serum sodium level was 145.72 ± 12.64 mgEq/L ranging from 126 to 166 mEq/L. Eighty one (80.2%) were term babies while 20 (19.8%) were pre-term babies. Of these 101 study cases, 29 (28.7%) delivered vaginally while 72 (71.3%) through cesarean section. Delayed crying was noted in 48 (47.5%), dehydration 13 (12.9%), sepsis in 36 (35.6%) and renal malformation in only 4%. Neonatal mortality in these patients was 15 (14.9%) while 86 (85.1%) were discharged from hospital after recovery.

Table-III: Serum Biochemical parameters with regards to delayed crying. (n=101)

Biochemical parameters		Delayed Crying		P-value
		Yes	No	
		Serum Potassium Level (mEq/L)	Mean	
	SD	0.83	0.94	
Serum Urea (mg/dl)	Mean	79.69	67.66	0.028
	SD	42.46	21.17	
Serum Sodium level (mEq/L)	Mean	146.79	144.75	0.422
	SD	9.41	15.02	

Table-IV: Serum Biochemical parameters with regards to sepsis. (n=101)

Biochemical parameters		Sepsis		P-value
		Yes	No	
Serum Potassium	Mean	4.52	5.18	0.001
Level (mEq/L)	SD	0.96	0.80	
Serum Urea	Mean	66.03	77.40	0.047
(mg/dl)	SD	18.35	31.06	
Serum Sodium	Mean	145.13	146.04	0.732
level (mEq/L)	SD	9.15	14.27	

DISCUSSION:

Different studies reported from various parts of the world have documented high prevalence of predisposing factors of acute renal failure in boys as compared with girls. Similarly in our study there were 75 (74.3%) boys while 26 (25.7%) were girls. From Iran also reported male to female ratio was 2.03:1 (67% versus 33%) showing same trends as that of our study results. Similar results have been reported by Airede et al. [18] Kandoth et al. [19] and Bourquia et al. [20] However Momtaz et al. [21] have reported different findings showing female gender predominating among newborns with AKI.

Acute renal failure is generally observed in first few days of life to couple of weeks time. Similarly in our study mean age of the newborns with AKI was 7.59 ± 6.13 days (range; 1 day to 28 days). Mean age of the boys was 5.73 ± 7.20 days while that of girls was 6.77 ± 6.16 days. ($p=0.515$). Gharehbaghi et al. [17] from Iran also reported 5.26 ± 6.2 days ranging from 2–28 days. Similarly, Momtaz et al.²¹ reported 7.7 ± 6.3 days mean age in newborns with AKI. Mean weight of these neonates was 2545.05 ± 600.42 grams (range; 1000 grams to 4000 grams). Gharehbaghi et al. [17] from Iran also reported 2682.58 ± 629.33 mean weight, close to our results.

In our study 80.2% were term babies while 19.8% were pre-term babies. Similarly, Gharehbaghi et al. [17] from Iran also reported 25.9% preterm deliveries. Momtaz et al. [21] documented 20.5% prematurity in newborns with acute renal failure.

Birth asphyxia and sepsis have been reported to be associated significantly with AKI in newborns all over the world [21-23] which may reach as higher as 78% in some studies. Delayed crying and sepsis were noted 47.5% and 35.6% respectively. Airede et al. [18] and Gharehbaghi et al.¹⁷ also reported similar results. High mortality rates have already been reported by different authors in children suffering from acute renal failure, in our study mortality rate was 14.9%. Gharehbaghi et al.¹⁷ from Iran also reported 20% mortality rate. In our study mortality was significantly higher in girls which is in compliance to similar results reported by Gharehbaghi et al.¹⁷ Momtaz et al.²¹ reported 36.7% mortality rate and also documented its association with female gender. However the reasons for this significant association of mortality in girls are not yet known. Similarly serum urea and serum sodium levels were also significantly higher in newborns with mortality. Other studies have documented sepsis as an underlying cause of mortality in these newborns, however our study results show different trends as this association was not statistically significant.

Table-V: Serum Biochemical parameters with regards to dehydration. (n=101)

Biochemical parameters		Dehydration		P-value
		Yes	No	
Serum Potassium	Mean	5.30	4.89	0.702
Level (mEq/L)	SD	0.68	0.93	
Serum Urea	Mean	76.00	72.95	0.070
(mg/dl)	SD	26.06	28.01	
Serum Sodium	Mean	150.84	144.96	0.017
level (mEq/L)	SD	6.61	13.16	

CONCLUSION:

Acute kidney disease in newborns is associated with significant disease morbidity and mortality with asphyxia and sepsis are the main etiological factors responsible. It is predominantly more common in boys compared with girls. Mortality rate was high in our study and it was significantly associated with female gender. Mortality was also associated with elevated serum sodium and urea level.

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